

Betty's (Re)Search Engine

A client-based search engine for research software stored in repositories. - Demonstration

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Motivation:

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- The process of finding research software for a specific purpose is inefficient.
- One must look through a publication before being able to hope for a corresponding link to a repository where the research software is then stored.
- The described way of searching also does not allow applying preferences (e.g., only searching for research software written in Python).

Betty's (Re)Searchengine

1. Send Request to Software Repositories
2. Response: corresponding repositories to a given Search Query
3. Send Request to Literature Platform
4. Response: Number of citations for a Repository
5. Sorting Repositories according to their number of citations

Demonstration

The screenshot shows the homepage of the Betty's (Re)Searchengine. At the top left is the TU Clausthal logo, and at the top right is the NFDI4ing logo. In the center, there is a logo consisting of a central circle connected to several smaller circles, with the text "Betty's (Re)Searchengine" to its right. Below the logo is a search bar with the placeholder text "Search" and a blue search button with a magnifying glass icon. Underneath the search bar are three links: "Link to our Paper", "What is this tool about?", and "Meet the Team behind this ...". At the bottom center of the page is a gear icon.

Challenges (1 / 2)

- Rate Limitations:
 - Every Service defines its own Rate Limitations.
 - Betty's (Re)Search Engine needs to deal with all of them while maintaining a sound workflow.

- Scalability:
 - Betty's (Re)Search Engine needs to be extendable with additional Services

- Parallelization:
 - A Search Process cannot be too time consuming, or else the user would lose interest

Whats under the hood

- APIs and Web Services are implemented as “Agents”
- They are instantiated and parallelized by the “Manager”
- The results are then stored in the Model

Whats next?

1. Send Request to Github API
2. Response: corresponding repositories
3. Send Request to Zenodo-API
4. Response: Number of citations for a Repository
5. Sorting Repositories according to their number of citations

Challenges (2 / 2)

- Computational Cost:
 - Multiple Processes are running within the user's browser.
- Linking Repositories to Research Papers:
 - Currently we're linking repositories to their corresponding research by searching explicitly for repositories that have a DOI in their README.
 - This approach however results in a limited amount of Repositories that we receive from GitHub.
 - Possible Solution: Conducting Full Text Search on external Databases
 - But then again we would have to deal with a great number of repositories that got nothing to do with research

Literatur

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